

A theory for developing infrastructure in developing countries using sustainable methods and clean, renewable energy:

1- Every gas station should have at least two electric vehicle charging points for solar-powered electric vehicles. These points should draw their energy from photovoltaic panels pre-installed on the roofs and canopies of the gas stations. This initiative should be mandatory for all gas stations nationwide.

2- All gas stations nationwide should have ATM machines equipped for both dispensing and depositing cash. This will allow station owners to deposit the price of the product into these machines, thus eliminating the need for a significant portion of cash transport vehicles and the associated security measures for both the vehicles and the ATMs.

3- Solar panels should be installed on the roofs of industrial areas and factories, interconnected, and connected to power refrigeration units for storing food, fruits, and meat.